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Coincidence photoelectron measurements following 2p photoionization in Mg

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Synopsis Coincidence photoelectron spectroscopy has been used to test the two-step model of Auger decay following 2p photoionization in magnesium. Fitting of the data has yielded information on the dipole photoionization matrix elements as a function of photon energy.

Photoelectron-Auger electron coincident measurements have been used to investigate 2p photoionization in magnesium. Generally, the angular distribution of the Auger electron depends on both the alignment of the core hole state and the contributing partial waves of the Auger decays. In specific cases, such as Mg 2p_{3/2} photoionization followed by L₃-M₁M₁ Auger decay, only a single partial wave contributes to the Auger decay and a measurement of the angular distribution of the Auger electron yields information about the alignment of the core-hole state [1]. This particular case led to a complete experiment, in which the dipole matrix elements were determined at a photon energy of 80 eV, without measurement of the spin of the electrons involved [2]. Similar information about the dynamics of the photoionization process [1] can be achieved by coincidence measurements of the photo- and Auger electrons, by a proper choice of the photoelectron angle.

In the present work the 2p_{3/2} photoelectron and the L₃-M₁M₁ Auger electron of Mg have been measured in coincidence after angle and energy selection. The experiments were performed with the multi-coincidence end-station of the Gas Phase beamline at Elettra. This setup contains ten hemispherical analyzers mounted on two independently rotatable frames. Three of the analyzers, in the plane of the linearly polarized incident light, direction ϵ , were fixed at 0, 30 and 60° with respect to ϵ , whilst the other seven, also mounted at 30° intervals in the same plane, were rotated in the plane perpendicular to the direction of propagation of the incident beam. This arrangement allows three triple differential cross-section (TDCS) data sets to be obtained simultaneously.

Sets of three TDCS measurements have been made at a range of photon energies. One made at 80 eV, allowed a direct comparison with previous measurements [3]. A simultaneous fit of the three TDCS indicates agreement with the predictions of the two-step model [1] and yields

information on the dipole matrix elements at 80 eV. A similar fitting procedure carried out at other photon energies, shows that the two-step predictions become less valid as the photon energy is reduced and final state interactions, such as post-collision interactions, become significant.

Figure 1. TDCS measured at 80 eV for three different photoelectron angles (indicated by the arrows) with respect to the polarization axis (ϵ), (i) 0°, (ii) 30° and (iii) 60°. The angle of emission of the Auger electron is indicated by the polar angle (θ_2). The solid lines in the polar plots are smoothed representations of the data. The bottom panel shows a simultaneous fit to all three TDCS, using the two-step model [1].

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